

THE EFFECTS OF PLAY-BASED READING INTERVENTION ON THE PHONICS SKILLS OF THE PRE-IDENTIFIED GRADE-3 NON-READERS

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ABSTRACT

With the growing number of non-readers during the post-pandemic period, the teaching-learning process has been hampered. Reading remediation was made to bridge these learning gaps. However, since learning paces differ for each learner, some students still have difficulty recognizing even simple words. Thus, this research is conducted to determine the effects of the play-based reading intervention to the phonics skills of pre-identified grade 3 non-readers. This study utilized the embedded sequential mixed method which is experimental in nature. It comprised both quantitative and qualitative method of gathering data. Thirty pre-identified Grade 3 non-readers were purposively selected to participate in this study. The CORE Phonics Test was used for the quantitative data of the study while FGD was used to gather the needed qualitative data. The findings revealed that the first step of addressing reading problems is giving attention to students with reading difficulties. The study also revealed that the use of play-based learning as a reading intervention can help in improving the level of students' phonics skills especially in identifying letter names and letter sounds. It also increased students' motivation to participate. However, it will not guarantee reading success for students with major reading problems. The study also revealed that absenteeism and interest plays an important role in the reading success of the students.

Keywords: *play-based learning, reading intervention, phonics skills, reading difficulties*

INTRODUCTION

Learning to read is a crucial educational aim for children. It opens up new opportunities, enables children to acquire new knowledge, and to do things needed in everyday living. Reading is a fundamental life skill that is very important for everyday living and future development. It is also imperative for children to learn it at an earlier stage.

However, the fact remains that there are learners who have reading difficulty, including slow reading speed, poor comprehension, omission of words, reversals of letters or words, decoding troubles, and limited vocabulary. It has become even more challenging when children grow older and have not moved beyond the primer or pre-primer stage. Clearly, children who grow up to be adults with low literacy levels are at a disadvantage in a culture that is placing ever-increasing expectations on proficient reading abilities in the workplace (Torgesen, 2002).

According to Campbell (2016), one of the most important indicators of future reading performance is phonological understanding. Children who have some familiarity with alphabet letters and sounds have a better understanding the alphabetic concept. Before kids can start decoding texts, they are required to understand the sounds of letters and its combination. The goal of phonics approaches is successful reading.

On the other hand, one of the most extensively studied topics in the early literacy field is the relationship between play and literacy. There is broad agreement that play is effective for learning and crucial for literacy development (Wood, 2017).

According to UNICEF, from ages 2-8, play is still essential for the development of children. At the age of 6-8 years old, considered the early grades in primary school, play-based learning approaches are still of great benefit. The study also showed that active, play-based experiences in language-rich environments help children develop their ideas about symbols, oral language, and the printed word, which are all vital components of reading (UNICEF, 2018).

With the growing number of non-readers during this post-pandemic period, the teaching-learning process has been hampered. In Alabel Central Integrated SPED Center, the result of the PHIL-IRI pre-test conducted during the beginning of school year 2022-2023 showed that out of 439 Grade 3 students, only 51 students are at the Independent level, 60 students are at the Instructional level, 147 students are at the Frustration level, and 183 students are Non-readers. Thus, reading interventions have been conducted in each classroom setting. However, since learning paces differ for each learner, some students still have difficulty recognizing even simple words.

For this particular study, the researcher conducted a study to determine the impact of the play-based reading intervention on the phonic skills of the pre-identified Grade-3 non-readers of Alabel Central Integrated SPED Center.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the impact of the play-based reading intervention on the phonic skills of pre-identified Grade-3 non-readers.

Specifically, the researcher seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of phonic skills of pre-identified Grade-3 non-readers before intervention in terms of:
 - 1.1 Alphabet Skills and Letter Sounds;
 - 1.2 Reading and Decoding Skills
2. What is the level of phonic skills of pre-identified Grade-3 non-readers after intervention in terms of:
 - 2.1 Alphabet Skills and Letter Sounds;
 - 2.2 Reading and Decoding Skills?
3. Is there a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test of Phonics Skills of pre-identified Grade-3 non-readers in terms of:
 - 3.1. Alphabet Skills and Letter Sounds;
 - 3.2. Reading and Decoding Skills?
4. How do the learners feel about their experiences with play-based reading intervention?

METHODOLOGY

This study used an embedded sequential mixed method approach since it aimed to determine the effects of an intervention on the level of their phonics skills and their experiences during the intervention. The embedded sequential mixed-methods design is done in a setting where quantitative data is prioritized, and qualitative data is used to supplement it (Creswell & Clark, 2017). Figure 1 depicts the research flow of this study.

Figure 1. Research Design

The respondents of the study were thirty (30) Grade-3 learners of Alabel Central Integrated SPED Center. They were purposively selected by Grade-3 classroom advisers of each class/section to join the reading remediation based on the following criteria: (a) non-readers; (b) can hardly identify alphabet and letter sounds; (c) has difficulty reading and decoding even simple CVC-patterned words; (d) identified to be in need of immediate reading intervention.

CORE Phonics Survey was adopted and used to determine the qualitative data before and after the study. Lesson plans were developed based from the CORE Phonics skills. It was also developed using the 4A's to which play activities were integrated and used in the teaching-learning process. These lesson plans served as a guide in the administration of the play-based reading intervention.

Focus Group Discussion (FGD) was also administered on all participants after the play-based reading intervention. The questions included in FGD were validated by 6 validators which comprises of 3 Master Teachers, 1 School Reading Coordinator, 1 Grade-3 Reading Coordinator, and 1 Grade-3 English Teacher of Alabel Central Integrated SPED Center using a 5-point rating scale assessment and validation tool.

In gathering the needed data, the following procedure were done. The first phase involved the collecting and analyzing of quantitative data. The quantitative data was in a form of a quasi-experimental method where pre-test of the CORE Phonics Survey was administered first in order to determine their phonics skills level. Play-based reading intervention followed and lasted for 30 sessions. Play-based reading intervention lessons followed the 4A format as requirement for DEPED Teachers. In the process of the intervention, play-based learning was integrated in the lesson. During the conduct of the intervention, the researcher noted some observations regarding students' performance, responses, and attitude towards play. After the reading intervention, a post-test of the CORE Phonics Survey was administered to determine if there is a significant difference on students' Phonics Skills.

The second phase of the data gathering procedure focused on the qualitative. For the qualitative data, focus group discussion was done to determine how the students feel about their experiences with play-based reading intervention. Overall results were then gathered and analyzed for interpretation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At the start of the study, the pre-identified Grade 3 non-readers were given a Pre-Assessment Test using CORE Phonics. Table 1 shows the CORE Phonics Test Scores of 30 students.

Table 1. CORE Phonics Survey Pre-Test Result

Level	Alphabet Skills and Letter Sounds (83 Items)	%	Reading and Decoding Skills (129 Items)	%
Benchmark	0	0	0	0
Strategic	0	0	0	0
Intensive	30	100%	30	100%
Mean	26.27	<i>Intensive</i>	0.01	<i>Intensive</i>

It shows that in an 83-item test in Alphabet Skills and Letter Sounds, all the participants scored in the range of Intensive level which means all student participants can hardly determine letter names of uppercase and lowercase letters, consonant sounds, long vowel sounds and short vowel sounds. This further shows that the level of phonic skills of pre-identified Grade-3 non-readers before the intervention was Intensive having an over-all mean score of 26.27. None of the participants scored in Strategic and Benchmark level.

The table also shows that in a 129 item test in Reading and Decoding Skills, there are no students who scored in Benchmark and Strategic. It shows that all of their test scores were only within the range of Intensive Level with an over-all mean score of 0.01. This can be interpreted that before the start of the reading intervention, all student participants could not decode the following sub-skills in Reading and Decoding such as short vowels in CVC words, consonant blends with short vowels, words with short vowels, digraphs, and –tch trigraph, words with R-controlled vowels, words with variant vowels, low frequency vowel and consonant spelling words, and multisyllabic words.

As presented on Table 1, it clearly shows that the pre-identified Grade-3 non-readers have little to no knowledge of letter names and sounds. As a result, their reading and decoding skills were also affected.

According to Campbell (2016), one of the most important indicators of future reading performance is phonological understanding. At the beginning of formal instruction, children who have some familiarity with alphabet letters and sounds have a better chance of understanding the alphabetic concept. The alphabetic principle requires children to pay attention to small units of sound and map these sounds of letters, or combinations of letters, which is a required skill for decoding written texts. Before kids can start decoding texts, they need to have had a variety of literacy-rich experiences, like chances to practice speaking out loud.

Furthermore, according to Light and McNaughton (2019), learning the letter names and sounds is the most basic skill a child should learn. Phonological awareness and knowledge of letter-sound correspondences are the fundamental components of learning

to read and write. These abilities are important indicators of how successfully children will learn to read. Thus, when the student has difficulty identifying letter names and sounds, they will also likely to have difficulty in Reading and Decoding Skills.

Table 2. CORE Phonics Survey Post-Test Result

Level	Alphabet Skills and Letter Sounds (83 Items)	%	Reading and Decoding Skills (129 Items)	%
Benchmark	5	16.67%	3	10%
Strategic	18	60%	9	30%
Intensive	7	23.33%	18	60%
Mean	69.17	Strategic	58.73	Intensive

After the reading intervention, the pre-identified Grade 3 non-readers were given the same set of assessment tests. Table 2 shows the CORE Phonics Test Scores of 30 students.

As shown in Table 2, there were significant improvements among the students after the play-based reading intervention in Alphabet Skills and Letter Sounds. In the previous table presented, no students managed to score in Benchmark and Strategic. However, based on the data presented in Table 2, five (5) students scored in the Benchmark with a percentage of 16.67. Eighteen students improved to Strategic level with a percentage of 60%, and only 7 students remained in the Intensive level which is 23.33% of the over-all participants.

Furthermore, students had also shown improvement in Reading and Decoding Skills after the play-based reading intervention. The data presented from the previous table shows that there were none who scored in the Benchmark and Strategic Level. However, after the intervention, data shows that 3 students scored in the Benchmark Level which comprised 10% of the total participants, 9 students became Strategic which is 30% of the total participants and 18 students remained in the Intensive Level which is 60% of the total participants.

Overall, data shows that the Phonics Skills of pre-identified Grade-3 Non-readers in Alphabet Skills and Letter Sounds have moved from Intensive to Strategic having an over-all mean score of 69.1. This shows that with the help of play-based reading intervention, students could already determine most of the letter names in uppercase and lowercase, consonant sounds, long vowels, and short vowels.

On the other hand, the level of Phonics Skills for Reading and Decoding Skills still remained Intensive having an overall mean score of 58.73. It shows that students still have difficulty in reading and decoding short vowels in CVC words, words in consonant blends with short vowels, words in short vowels, digraphs, and -tch trigraph, words with R-controlled vowels, words with long vowel spellings, words with variant vowels, words with low frequency and consonant spellings, and multisyllabic words.

Nevertheless, from the data presented, it is notable that test scores from the pre-test and post-test showed improvement after the play-based reading intervention. Several factors might be considered as well in the students' reading development including the number of days the intervention lasted. The intervention was conducted for only 15 days or 30 sessions. Thus, progress may be considered slow.

According to Roe et al. (2018), the goal of phonics approaches is successful reading; they are not meant to be ends in and of themselves. Students are assisted in matching spoken and written words, and they laid the foundation for creating their decoding techniques. Phonic techniques help students recognize words they understand in oral form. Campbell (2016) also added that before beginning formal schooling, a child's capacity to recognize letter names and shapes is a powerful indicator of their success in reading later on. Letter sounds vary depending on where they are placed in a word, but letter names stay the same. Because of this, the reading decoding approach known as "sounding out" complete words may not always be successful.

Furthermore, according to Light and McNaughton (2019), in order for a child to learn to reading, the learner must first identify the letters in the word, then link each letter to its sound, memorize the sounds in order, blend the sounds to form the word, and then recall the word's meaning in order to decode words.

This study likewise determined whether there was a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of the students with the use of the play-based reading intervention. A Test for Normality (Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test) was performed to determine if the data gathered were normally distributed or not. Since the data turned out to be not normally distributed, a non-parametric test, Mann-Whitney U-test, was utilized to determine if there was a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test scores. All data were also tested using 0.05 level of significance.

From the data presented in Table 1 and 2, and the non-parametric test conducted, data for Phonics Skills specifically for Alphabet Skills and Letter Sounds and Reading and Decoding Skills were summarized in the following table below:

**Table 3.a Differences between Pre-Test and Post-test Scores
in Alphabet Skills and Letter Sounds**

Test	Mean	Mean Ranks	Mann-Whitney <i>U</i>	<i>p</i> -value	Remarks
Pre-Test	26.27	18.07	823	0.0000	Significant
Post-Test	69.17	42.93	77	0.0000	

**Tested at 0.05 level of significance*

As shown on the table, the mean of the pre-test scores of the students before the reading intervention was only 26.27 which was also considered an Intensive level having a mean rank of 18.07. However, after the play-based reading intervention, the mean of their test scores had improved drastically into 69.17 with mean rank of 42.93. Their level had moved from **Intensive** to **Strategic**.

In addition, since the *p*-value (0.0000) is less than 0.05, there is a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the Phonics Skills of pre-identified Grade-3 non-readers in terms of Alphabet Skills and Letter Sounds.

This data shows that the play-based reading intervention has greatly helped non-readers to develop their skills in identifying letter names and sounds such as the skills in determining names of uppercase and lowercase letters, determining consonants and vowels sounds, as well as identifying long and short vowels sounds. This data has further proven that using play-based learning activities at the age of 8 is still beneficial despite having reading difficulties.

This findings is in consonance with what the UNICEF (2018) hast stated that ages of 6 and 8, children are regarded to be in the early grades of primary school. Play-based learning is still important, although it is sometimes overlooked in favor of academic-focused education techniques. Active, play-based learning techniques can, ultimately, enhance children's educational experiences in the early primary grades and improve learning motivation and outcomes throughout this time. Thus, play is essential for learning and growth in the early years. Play is one of the most critical methods for young children to acquire crucial knowledge and abilities.

**Table 3.b Differences between Pre-Test and Post-test Scores
in Reading and Decoding Skills**

Test	Mean	Mean Ranks	Mann-Whitney <i>U</i>	<i>p</i> -value	Remarks
Pre-Test	0.10	16.08	822.5	0.0000	Significant
Post-Test	58.73	44.92	17.5	0.0000	

**Tested at 0.05 level of significance*

In the table presented, the mean in the pre-test in Reading and Decoding Skills is only 0.10. It has a mean rank of 16.08 while in the post-test the mean score increased to 58.73 with a mean rank of 44.92. It can be observed that there is a movement among the scores presented.

In addition, the level of phonic skills of pre-identified Grade 3 learners after the intervention moved but still remained in **Intensive** level. However, since the *p*-value (0.0000) is less than 0.05, there is a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the Phonics Skills of pre-identified Grade-3 non-readers in terms of their Reading and Decoding Skills.

It has shown that the use of play-based learning or play-based activities during the reading intervention helped for significant improvement on the student's performance. It was also shown that the use of playful and interactive learning is essential and effective for a child's learning development. Though the level of their Reading and Decoding Skills has not improved, it is still evident in the data presented that there was an improvement with their test scores.

Furthermore, since these students could not identify letter names and letter sounds at the start of the remediation, and the intervention lasted only for 30 sessions, it is understandable that not all of them could read immediately. However, the use of play and different learning materials would help them improve with continuous use in a classroom's teaching and learning process.

In fact, according to Wardle (2008) play fosters the development of several abilities that are essential for children to learn to read and write later in life. As a result of their language development through play, children can better convey their thoughts. Phonics is a method of teaching reading that emphasizes the development of letter-sound correspondences and their application in reading and spelling.

These results are also in consonance with Roskos & Christie (2011) view that the presence of literacy materials and tools in the environment encourages literacy

interactions during play. Literacy concepts and abilities are stimulated into play activity through adult interaction and intervention. In addition, Omega & Alieto (2019) had found out that when children are actively involved in the play, their ability to learn advances, and play has become a primary means for them to an expression of ideas, feelings, and beliefs.

These only shows that play is undeniably beneficial to children's development in every way. Teaching and learning through play have been demonstrated to benefit a child's language development and reading ability. Indeed, teaching and learning through play is the most effective technique to enhance preschool teachers' teaching methods while also developing children's language abilities. Ali et al (2011) had also showed in their findings which is relative to the findings stated in this study that teaching and learning through play could help youngsters strengthen their reading abilities while keeping their attention.

Students' Feelings On The Play-Based Reading Intervention

Based on the Focused Group Discussion, all students were asked on how they feel before, during and after reading intervention. Their responses are summarized as follows.

Students' Feelings Before The Intervention

When students cannot read, it is expected that they would feel sad, nervous, shy, or anxious. However, most of the students said they felt happy. During the focus group discussion, these students were asked why they were happy. Students stated that they were happy

“kay napilian ko nga muapil sa pabasa cher”
(because I was selected to be part of the reading intervention), and

“kay matudluan na jud ko mubasa cher
(because finally someone will teach me how to read).

Since students' needs were properly given attention, and their peers inside the classroom were all non-readers, students felt a sense of belongingness and they felt happy with it.

According to Commodari and Guarnera (2005), in their study “Attention and Reading Skills”, attention plays a crucial part in the processing of information. Attention is needed for the proper development of complex cognitive skills and academic achievement.

However, when students cannot read and decode even simple words, they show different negative feelings. Most students during the focus group discussion said that they feel nervous when they are called to read. When asked why they felt nervous, some participants narrated that they felt nervous

*“kay basin kasab-an mi ni teacher pag di mi makabasa”
(because we might be scoled if we couldn’t read),*

while other students said;

*“maulaw ko cher kay dli ko sigurado if mabasa naku”
(I felt shy because I’m not confident if I can read the words).*

According to Cambria and Guthrie (2010), more than any other incentive in school, self-confidence is the factor that most strongly correlates with success. The explanation is that success is closely related to confidence, which is the belief in one's own abilities. For routine, everyday reading tasks, this connection is present. A student who reads a page in a book quickly assumes that he can read the next page in the same book quickly as well. The connection is faked for reading in general as well. A student who reads easily and comprehends material effectively is confident in his or her reading ability. People like the things they do well both inside and outside of school.

Students who have difficulty, on the other hand, start to question their skills. They anticipate performing poorly when reading, writing, and discussing a text. The actual problem is that underachievers frequently overestimate their limitations. They give up because they think they are worse than they actually are. By withdrawing from all text interactions, they lessen their own opportunity to do what they value reading the most. Their lack of self-assurance further damages them in a circle of failure and doubt. For many students, a rapport of trust with their teacher is the one factor that matters in developing their confidence.

Students Feelings During the Reading Intervention

When the teacher gave reading activities through play, students had positive responses. They said during the discussion that they felt happy, motivated, and excited. Most participants said

*“lingaw kaayo cher “,
“sadya kaayo magdula cher”, and
“makaexcite magdula na pud cher.”*

Students feelings towards play are also in accordance with Whitebread (2017) had stated that play is joyful and that children regularly smile and laugh while playing. In a general sense, they feel satisfaction, motivation, thrill, and pleasure.

According to Cambria and Guthrie (2010), we can choose to ignore motivation. However if we do, we might be skipping over the most crucial aspect of reading. Reading has two sides to it. The skills, such as phonemic awareness, phonics, word identification, vocabulary, and rudimentary understanding, are on one side. The want or the “will” to read is on the other side. A skilled reader is one who wills to read. We are referring to reading motivation when we talk about the "will" part. This depicts how kids feel about reading, what they want, and how they behave. A pupil may be capable even with competence, but he cannot become a reader without will. Her ability to exercise willpower

determines whether she becomes a student who appreciates and benefits from literacy by reading widely and frequently.

In addition, UNICEF (2018) stated that active, play-based learning techniques could, ultimately, enhance children's educational experiences in the early primary grades and improve learning motivation and outcomes throughout this time. Thus, play is essential for learning and growth in the early years. Play is one of the most critical methods for young children to acquire crucial knowledge and abilities.

Furthermore, Wohlwend (2015) stated that when reading and play activities are merged, they complement and reinforce one another, expanding the number of methods for children to "do school" and allowing more varied learners to participate.

During the play-based reading intervention, several games were included. Some of these games were post it, sack race, paper plane, IT, chinese garter and etc. Among the games given, based from the focus group discussion, the game "IT" is what the students like best. Most students said that they like it because

"lingaw cher"
(It is fun),

some said

"kay ganahan ko cher"
(I like it),

S1 and S5 specifically answered with

"kay makadagan dagan ko cher"
(because I can freely run).

The play "IT" belongs to the Physical Type of play, which is the oldest kind of play. Physical play has been connected to motor development, and there is some preliminary evidence that it is also linked to social development (UNICEF, 2018).

It is evident that a play where students could feel free is more likely enjoyable for them. During the intervention, students strive hard to read the words attached to their peers, which they tagged as "IT", or they will remain as "IT" throughout the game.

According to Wood (2017), play should be joyful and interactive so that students may be encouraged to interact with the language and be thrilled by the possibilities.

Students were also asked of the game that they had experienced difficulty with. Paper plane, bottle bowling, IT, word domino, pick the word, and hit the bell were some of the games included in the reading intervention. These were also the games students said they had experienced difficulty. However, the game Bottle Bowling had been more difficult to most of the students. During the discussion, they were asked why they had difficulties with Bottle Bowling. S23 and S25 relatively said,

*“dili man ko sure unsa sulod na words sa bote nga akong maigo cher”
(I am not sure of the words inside the bottle.)*

Some students said,

*“dili ko kaigo cher”
(I can't hit the bottle!)*

while S14 said,

*“kay wala man ko sa mood cher”
(I'm not in the mood).*

According to Cambria and Guthrie (2010), researchers refer to interest as intrinsic motivation. Interest became a motivating factor for students to do a task or not. During the game “Bottle Bowling”, the researcher observed that when students could not hit their target, they felt unmotivated. And/or if they have a group mate that doesn't want to participate, it also changes their mood. Sometimes, when students feel that they cannot grasp or perform the activity well, it also affects their performance.

Furthermore, when students were asked if it easier to learn reading while they play, almost all students said yes. They said that learning while playing is fun and they felt happy

“kay lingaw man ug makalipay”,

and they also felt motivated

“kay maganahan man mi”.

Their responses align with the UNICEF (2018) that active, play-based learning techniques can, ultimately, enhance children's educational experiences in the early primary grades and improve learning motivation and outcomes throughout this time. Thus, play is essential for learning and growth in the early years. Play is one of the most critical methods for young children to acquire crucial knowledge and abilities.

On the other hand, S14 who solely answered with ‘No’ said that it is not easier to learn reading when he plays with the reason

*“kay pirmi man ko absent cher, di ko kaapil sa dula”
(since I am always absent and cannot join the game).*

It only shows that absenteeism is still a factor to consider why other students remain non-readers even after intervention. From the data presented in Table 1 and 2, some students still scored low in Alphabet Skills and Reading and Decoding Skills because they missed several remediation sessions in a week.

This is in consonance with the study conducted by Gottfried (2014) on “*Chronic Absenteeism and Its Effects on Students' Academic and Socio-emotional Outcomes*” that absenteeism affects pupils' chances of succeeding even in kindergarten. Chronic

absences have a negative impact on academic performance in math and reading as well as social and academic engagement.

Students' Feelings After the Play-Based Reading Intervention

After the reading intervention, students were asked how they feel. Most students said they felt happy and excited. Since it is the end of the reading intervention, it is understandable that students would feel happy and excited to go back to their own classrooms. However, some said they felt sad. During the focus group discussion, these students narrated why they were sad. S24 said

*“mas nalingaw man ko magbasa basa cher”
(we enjoyed the reading intervention),*

S25 and S30 even asked

*“pwede diri ra sa mi sa imung room cher?
(Can we stay here longer?),*

S30 even added that she felt sad because

*“dili ko gusto mahuman ang pabasa cher”
(I do not want the intervention to end.)*

It only shows that play generally satisfies a basic human desire to express imagination, curiosity, and creativity, all of which are great tools in today's knowledge-based environment. They assist in coping, finding joy, and utilizing our creative and ingenious abilities. Indeed, the essential building blocks of the future are the crucial skills children gain through play (UNICEF, 2018).

In addition, students were asked if they like to have play-based activities with other subjects. Almost all students said 'Yes'. When they were asked what subject, most of them answered with Mathematics while others said English and Filipino. S1 and S2 said they like to have play activities in Mathematics

*“para makabalo ko muihap cher”
(so I could learn how to count),*

while most students said

*“para lingaw”
(so we could have fun).*

According to Peck (2022), the 21st-century students learn by doing and having fun. Teachers must integrate it into everyday tasks. When students learn a job through play, they retain it much more quickly and for longer than when they merely complete a worksheet.

Therefore, since the beginning, games have always been a necessary component of education. They have significantly changed the educational environment by emphasizing learner-centric pedagogy. The educational games can be seen as a modern interpretation of these age-old theories and methods for teaching students' language, logic, and mathematical abilities.

In general, and as seen from all the quantitative and qualitative data presented, play is an essential strategy for learning and teaching. The active, play-based learning techniques can, ultimately, enhance children's educational experiences and improve learning motivation and outcomes on students. It is one of the most critical methods for young children to acquire crucial knowledge and abilities.

In addition, children benefit from play-based learning because they can express themselves and improve their language abilities. Play is undeniably beneficial to children's development in every way. Teaching and learning through play have been demonstrated to benefit a child's language development and reading ability. Also, proper learning materials, manipulative tools and other interactive activities should be carefully selected and used in every activity to make the teaching-learning process more effective.

However, despite the efforts to prepare all the materials necessary, preparing interactive and fun play activities, and use play as a tool in teaching, absenteeism remains a factor that affects reading development among other non-readers. Motivation also plays a vital role in which a child could learn.

Furthermore, based on the observations of the researcher during the interview and the conduct of the reading intervention, some of the students show manifestations and signs of a maybe more serious reading problems that needs clinical intervention and diagnosis based on how they interact, answer, and write letters. This may also be a factor why it would be difficult for them to read and decode even simple words.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher had drawn the following conclusions: (a) The first step on addressing reading problems is identifying and giving proper attention to students with reading difficulties; (b) The pre-identified Grade 3 non-readers' level of Phonics Skills is Intensive both in Alphabet Skills and Letter Sounds and in Reading and Decoding before the start of the play-based reading intervention but improved to Strategic Level in Alphabet Skills and Letter Sounds and remained in Intensive Level in Reading and Decoding Skills after the intervention; (c) The play-based reading intervention helped in improving the level of students' phonics skills especially in identifying letter names and letter sounds; (d) The play-based reading intervention increase the level of students motivation and participation, but it will not guarantee reading success for students with major reading problems; (e) Absenteeism and Motivation are some of the factors to be considered why some students remain non-readers; and (f) when signs of reading difficulties are evident on students, proper communication to parents and proper diagnosis from experts should be encouraged.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are hereby given: the use of play-based activities is highly encouraged in the teaching-learning process. Teachers could use the play-based method in teaching beginning or non-readers who have little to no knowledge of alphabet skills. It would help them familiarize, and identify letter names and sounds in a fun and enjoyable way. If used in a short period of time, it will not guarantee to make a child become a reader. Nevertheless, teachers could use play-based methods to motivate students to participate.

In addition, since the study is only limited to 30 sessions, it would be recommendable for future researchers to further conduct the study in a longer period using both the play-based and the traditional types of teaching reading.

Furthermore, other researchers could also investigate if the use of play-based strategies in other subjects like Mathematics could help improve numeracy skills among students.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical approval for this study was waved by the Mindanao State University – General Santos City Institutional Ethics Committee (MSU-GSC IERC) based on the following provisions: (1) The study involves a survey that is non-sensitive in nature, and (2) The names of the participants are anonymized.

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